

Open & Transparent Research Practices

Case Study – Economics

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Introduction

Openness and transparency constitute a foundational principle for research integrity, as set out in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. Openness can promote rigour, constructive scrutiny, accountability and can enable others to build on research. However, it can also bring challenges. Critically, what openness and transparency can and should mean varies across disciplines and fields of study. This is one of a series of case studies in a wide range of disciplines that illustrate these differences. The series is intended to enable researchers to see similarities and differences between fields, and to inform those supporting open research through, for example, training, policies or incentives. This case study is from the field of Economics. It is based on a single interview with a researcher, and is therefore illustrative rather than representative.

Background

The field of Economics concerns the study of how individuals and society choose to use scarce resources, mainly for the production, distribution, and consumption of commodities. Two major branches are often highlighted: micro-economics, the study of the economic behaviours of individuals, households and companies, and macro-economics, concerning larger-scale regional, national and global groups. A number of sub-disciplines exist in both branches. Examples range from the study of fiscal policy, growth, and inflation (macro), to the study of costs, production and game theory (micro).

The interviewee is an Associate Professor of Economics, who started their career researching game theory. Their work has expanded to include the study of cooperation, often related to addressing large social and societal issues such as climate change, poverty, and inequality. Another focus is on organisations, helping them to solve internal problems related to race, gender, and others, helping them to harness these demographics effectively.

A variety of methods are used to complete this research, from traditional experimental methods employed by economists (such as randomised controlled trials), to using modern Computer Science methods (such as modelling, simulation and machine learning) on big data. Resulting articles are published in peer-reviewed journals, including Nature, and Nature Human Behaviour.

Relevance of openness & transparency

Publishing in top Economics journals is challenging, and requires researchers to be exceptionally rigorous with their methodology, itself a form of transparency. In addition, further levels of openness are now required, with publication of code, data, and pre-registration all expected, especially for larger studies in top journals. As a result, it is now more common for research groups to write code with the assumption that it will be made public from the start of the project.

An area in Economics research where openness and transparency must be treated carefully is when working with commercial organisations. In many cases, research funding will be supplied by a government, or a non-governmental organisation, and then involve a separate commercial entity, such as a business workplace, who help gain access to participants. However, commercial organisations can also approach economists directly to perform highly-specific consulting work for them. This needs to be managed carefully by academics to avoid serious conflict of interest.

The openness of data can also depend on the involvement of these partner organisations. On one end of the scale, when researchers collect and fully control data used for research, this can be de-identified and published. On the other, data (and even research) produced in consultancy projects might never be made available. Between these, many flavours exist, necessitating a case-by-case approach. One example is where organisations allow publication of research results, but retain publishing rights over the data collected by researchers. However, if a second research group wanted to use this data set, a new sharing agreement with the organisation could be put in place, allowing both groups to then use it.

Pros and cons of openness & transparency

As discussed, the rigour and detail that Economists must treat and explain their methods when publishing leads to a natural degree of openness. This is also helped by pre-registration documents. These standards thus provide a positive feedback loop: high publication requirements require high levels of research clarity, explanation and transparency, which require a high level of domain understanding by academics, which helps to keep publication requirements elevated.

These exceptionally high publishing requirements have potentially helped the field avoid some of the replication crisis experienced by other Social Sciences, such as Psychology. As in other disciplines, replication of research can help its generalisability to other organisations and societal groups. Similar to other disciplines, code/methods and data are generally required to achieve this. However, data publication is often embargoed, with organisations concerned about making sensitive data about their employees or workplace accessible, resulting in a lower rate of replication.

Barriers to the publication of research also exist, especially when null results are found. In one example, an experiment was conducted in one location in a country, which could have been publishable on its own; however, an additional replication experiment was subsequently conducted at a different location in the country, yielding a null result. A decision was made to halt publication, in case non-generalisable evidence was being produced. This conservative approach meant missing out on a paper in the short term, but potentially had reputational benefits in the future. For career-orientated academics, trade-offs between openness and career progression might be difficult to manage.

Wider context & trends

Overall, openness in the field of Economics has come a long way, and is continuing to improve. There are areas that require further thought, in particular, questions regarding the safe and secure management and publication of proprietary data (especially sensitive medical data) remain unanswered. This could have great benefit to the research community, but must be approached carefully.

Economics researchers are often inwardly focused, adopting new methods via the publication of exceptional papers by renowned, trusted economists, and not via industry or researchers in other disciplines. This lack of openness to new methods from other fields slows their application to Economics, and reduces pace of research. An area where this is apparent is in the sub-discipline of Econometrics, and its slow adoption of machine learning methods from

Computer Science, occurring maybe 5-6 years ago. Their usage, trust and respect required an established Econometrician (Susan Athey) to champion them, before they could be widely adopted.

Compared to openness in other Social Sciences, Economics researchers feel that they are a step ahead in their journey. They have established good norms and practices, and kept standards high, which has not occurred in all other disciplines thus far. One explanation for this are the differing publication requirements, based on career pressures in each differing discipline. In Psychology, with many PhD students, long post-docs, and few available positions, career pressures are very high. In Economics, there are many individuals, but also many positions, and lower career pressures. In Management, there are lower pressures still. Researchers don't always conduct their best work when these pressures are high, and it is clear that integrity might be compromised in a less stable career setting.

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